

FUZZY VERSION OF SOFT UNION ACTION (SU-ACTION) ON NEAR-RING MODULE (N-MODULE) STRUCTURES

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Cite This Article: S. V. Manemaran, R. Nagarajan & Saleem Abdullah, “Fuzzy Version of Soft Union Action (SU-Action) on Near-Ring Module (N-Module) Structures”, International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Page Number 39-46, Volume 1, Issue 1, 2016

Abstract: In this paper, we define a new concept, called soft union action (SU) on N- module structures on a fuzzy soft set. This new notions gathers fuzzy theory, soft set theory and near-ring modulo theory (N-module theory) together and it shows how a fuzzy soft set effects on N-module structure in the mean of union and inclusion of sets. We then obtain its basic properties with illustrative examples and derive some analog of classical N-module theoretic concepts for SU-action on N-module. Finally, we give the application of SU-actions on N-module theory.

Keywords: Fuzzy Set, Soft Set, Fuzzy Soft Set, N-Module SU-Action, N-Ideal SU-action, α -Inclusion, Pre-Image & Soft Image.

AMS Mathematics Subject Classification: 03E70, 58E40

1. Introduction:

Soft set theory was introduced in 1999 by Molodtsov [22] for dealing with uncertainties and it has gone through remarkably rapid strides in the mean of algebraic structures as in [1, 2, 11, 14, 15, 16, 18, 25, 28]. Moreover, Atagun and Sezgin [4] defined the concepts of soft sub rings and ideals of a ring, soft subfields of a field and soft sub modules of a module and studied their related properties with respect to soft set operations. Operations of soft sets have been studied by some authors, too. Maji et al. [19] presented some definitions on soft sets and based on the analysis of several operations on soft sets Ali et al. [3] introduced several operations of soft sets and Sezgin and Atagun [26] studied on soft set operations as well. Furthermore, soft set relations and functions [5] and soft mappings [21] with many related concepts were discussed. The theory of soft set has also a wide-ranging applications especially in soft decision making as in the following studies: [6, 7, 23, 29]. In this paper, we define a new concept, called soft union action (SU) on N- module structures on a fuzzy soft set. This new notions gathers fuzzy theory, soft set theory and near-ring modulo theory (N-module theory) together and it shows how a fuzzy soft set effects on N-module structure in the mean of union and inclusion of sets. We then obtain its basic properties with illustrative examples and derive some analog of classical N-module theoretic concepts for SU-action on N-module. Finally, we give the application of SU-actions on N-module theory.

2. Preliminaries:

In this section, we recall some basic notions relevant to near-ring modules (N-modules) and fuzzy soft sets. By a near-ring, we shall mean an algebraic system $(N, +, \cdot)$,
 Where

(N₁) $(N, +)$ forms a group (not necessarily abelian)

(N₂) (N, \cdot) forms a semi group and

(N₃) $(x + y)z = xz + yz$ for all $x, y, z \in N$. (that is we study on right Near-ring modules)

Throughout this paper, N will always denote right near-ring. A normal subgroup H of N is called a left ideal of N if $n(s+h)-ns \in H$ for all $n, s \in N$ and $h \in H$ and denoted by $H \triangleleft_l N$. For a near-ring N, the zero-symmetric part of N denoted by N_0 is defined by $N_0 = \{n \in N \mid n0=0\}$. Let $(S, +)$ be a group and $A: N \times S \rightarrow S, (n, s) \rightarrow ns$. (S, A) is called N-module or near-ring module if for all $x, y \in N, s \in S$.

(i) $x(ys) = (xy)s$

(ii) $(x+y)s = xs+ys$. It is denoted by N^S . Clearly N itself is an N-module by natural operations. A subgroup T of N^S with $NT \subseteq T$ is said to be N-sub module of S and denoted by $T \leq_N S$. A normal subgroup T of S is called an N-ideal of N^S and denoted by a near-ring, S and χ two N-modules. Then $h: S \rightarrow \chi$ is called an N-homomorphism if $s, \delta \in S$, for all $n \in N$,

(i) $h(s+\delta) = h(s)+h(\delta)$ and

(ii) $h(ns) = nh(s)$.

For all undefined concepts and notions we refer to (24). From now on, U refers to on initial universe, E is a set of parameters $P(U)$ is the power set of U and $A, B, C \subseteq E$.

2.1 Definition [22]:

A pair (F, A) is called a soft set over U, where F is a mapping given by $F: A \rightarrow P(U)$. In other words, a soft set over U is a parameterized family of subsets of the universe U.

Note that a soft set (F, A) can be denoted by F_A . In this case, when we define more than one soft set in some subsets A, B, C of parameters E , the soft sets will be denoted by F_A, F_B, F_C , respectively. On the other case, when we define more than one soft set in a subset A of the set of parameters E , the soft sets will be denoted by F_A, G_A, H_A , respectively. For more details, we refer to [11, 17, 18, 26, 29, 7].

2.2 Definition [6]:

The relative complement of the soft set F_A over U is denoted by F_A^r , where $F_A^r: A \rightarrow P(U)$ is a mapping given as $F_A^r(a) = U \setminus F_A(a)$, for all $a \in A$.

2.3 Definition [6]:

Let F_A and G_B be two soft sets over U such that $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$. The restricted intersection of F_A and G_B is denoted by $F_A \Psi G_B$, and is defined as $F_A \Psi G_B = (H, C)$, where $C = A \cap B$ and for all $c \in C$, $H(c) = F(c) \cap G(c)$.

2.4 Definition [6]:

Let F_A and G_B be two soft sets over U such that $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$. The restricted union of F_A and G_B is denoted by $F_A \cup_R G_B$, and is defined as $F_A \cup_R G_B = (H, C)$, where $C = A \cap B$ and for all $c \in C$, $H(c) = F(c) \cup G(c)$.

2.5 Definition [12]:

Let F_A and G_B be soft sets over the common universe U and ψ be a function from A to B . Then we can define the soft set $\psi(F_A)$ over U , where $\psi(F_A): B \rightarrow P(U)$ is a set valued function defined by $\psi(F_A)(b) = \cup\{F(a) \mid a \in A \text{ and } \psi(a) = b\}$, if $\psi^{-1}(b) \neq \emptyset$, $= \emptyset$ otherwise for all $b \in B$. Here, $\psi(F_A)$ is called the soft image of F_A under ψ . Moreover we can define a soft set $\psi^{-1}(G_B)$ over U , where $\psi^{-1}(G_B): A \rightarrow P(U)$ is a set-valued function defined by $\psi^{-1}(G_B)(a) = G(\psi(a))$ for all $a \in A$. Then, $\psi^{-1}(G_B)$ is called the soft pre image (or inverse image) of G_B under ψ .

2.6 Definition [13]:

Let F_A and G_B be soft sets over the common universe U and ψ be a function from A to B . Then we can define the soft set $\psi^*(F_A)$ over U , where $\psi^*(F_A): B \rightarrow P(U)$ is a set-valued function defined by $\psi^*(F_A)(b) = \cap\{F(a) \mid a \in A \text{ and } \psi(a) = b\}$, if $\psi^{-1}(b) \neq \emptyset$, $= \emptyset$ otherwise for all $b \in B$. Here, $\psi^*(F_A)$ is called the soft anti image of F_A under ψ .

2.7 Definition [8]:

Let f_A be a soft set over U and α be a subset of U . Then, lower α -inclusion of a soft set f_A , denoted by $f^{\alpha}A$, is defined as $f^{\alpha}A = \{x \in A : f_A(x) \subseteq \alpha\}$

3. SU-Action on N-Module Structures and N-Ideal Structures with Fuzzy Version:

In this section, we first define fuzzy soft union action, abbreviated as fuzzy SU-action on N-module and N-ideal structures with illustrative examples. We then study their basic results with respect to soft set operation.

3.1 Definition:

Let S be an N-module and f_s be a fuzzy soft set over U , then f_s is called fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U if it satisfies the following conditions;

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(FS}_U\text{N-1)} \quad & f_s(x+y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y) \\ \text{(FS}_U\text{N-2)} \quad & f_s(-x) \subseteq f_s(x) \\ \text{(FS}_U\text{N-3)} \quad & f_s(nx) \subseteq f_s(x) \\ & \text{For all } x, y \in S \text{ and } n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned}$$

3.1 Example:

Consider the near-ring module $N = \{0, x, y, z\}$, be the near-ring under the operation defined by the following table:

+	0	x	y	z
0	0	x	y	z
x	x	0	z	y
y	y	z	0	x
z	z	y	x	0

.	0	x	y	z
0	0	0	0	0
x	x	x	x	x
y	0	0	0	0
z	x	x	x	x

Let $S=N$ and S be the set of parameters

and $U = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} a & a \\ 0 & a \end{bmatrix} \mid a, b \in Z_6 \right\}$, 2×2 matrices with Z_6 terms, is the universal set .we construct a fuzzy soft set.

$$\begin{aligned} f_s(0) &= \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 2 \\ 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 0 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \right\}, \quad f_s(x) = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 2 \\ 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 0 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \right\}, \\ f_s(y) &= \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 2 \\ 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \right\}, \quad \text{and } f_s(z) = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 2 \\ 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Then one can easily show that the soft set f_s is a fuzzy SU-action on N-module.

3.1 Proposition:

Let f_s be a fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U . Then, $f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(x)$ for all $x \in S$.

Proof:

Assume that f_s is fuzzy SU-action over U. Then, for all $x \in S$, $f_s(0) = f_s(x-x) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(-x) = f_s(x) \cup f_s(x) = f_s(x)$.

3.1 Theorem:

Let S be a fuzzy SU-action on N-module and f_s be a fuzzy soft set over U. Then f_s is SU-action of N-module over U if and only if

- (i) $f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y)$
- (ii) $f_s(nx) \subseteq f_s(x)$ for all $x, y \in S$ and $n \in N$.

Proof:

Suppose f_s is a fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U. Then, by definition-3.1,

$$f_s(xy) \subseteq f_s(y) \text{ and } f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(-y) = f_s(x) \cup f_s(y) \text{ for all } x, y \in S$$

Conversely, assume that $f_s(xy) \subseteq f_s(y)$ and $f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y)$ for all $x, y \in S$.

If we choose $x=0$, then $f_s(0-y) = f_s(-y) \subseteq f_s(0) \cup f_s(y) = f_s(y)$ by proposition-3.1. Similarly $f_s(y) = f_s(-(-y)) \subseteq f_s(-y)$, thus $f_s(-y) = f_s(y)$ for all $y \in S$. Also, by assumption

$$f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(-y) = f_s(x) \cup f_s(y). \text{ This completes the proof.}$$

3.2 Theorem:

Let f_s be a fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U.

- (i) If $f_s(x-y) = f_s(0)$ for any $x, y \in S$, then $f_s(x) = f_s(y)$.
- (ii) $f_s(x-y) = f_s(0)$ for any $x, y \in S$, then $f_s(x) = f_s(y)$.

Proof:

Assume that $f_s(x-y) = f_s(0)$ for any $x, y \in S$, then

$$f_s(x) = f_s(x-y+y) \subseteq f_s(x-y) \cup f_s(y) = f_s(0) \cup f_s(y) = f_s(y)$$

and similarly,

$$f_s(y) = f_s((y-x)+x) \subseteq f_s(y-x) \cup f_s(x) = f_s(-(y-x)) \cup f_s(x) = f_s(0) \cup f_s(x) = f_s(x)$$

Thus, $f_s(x) = f_s(y)$ which completes the proof. Similarly, we can show the result (ii).

It is known that if S is an N-module, then $(S,+)$ is a group but not necessarily abelian. That is, for any $x, y \in S$, $x+y$ needs not be equal to $y+x$. However, we have the following:

3.3 Theorem:

Let f_s be fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U and $x \in S$. Then, $f_s(x) = f_s(0) \Leftrightarrow f_s(x+y) = f_s(y+x) = f_s(y)$ for all $y \in S$.

Proof:

Suppose that $f_s(x+y) = f_s(y+x) = f_s(y)$ for all $y \in S$. Then, by choosing $y = 0$, we obtain that $f_s(x) = f_s(0)$.

Conversely, assume that $f_s(x) = f_s(0)$. Then by proposition-3.1, we have

$$f_s(0) = f_s(x) \subseteq f_s(y), \forall y \in S \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Since f_s is fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U, then

$$f_s(x+y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y) = f_s(y), \forall y \in S. \text{ Moreover, for all } y \in S$$

$$f_s(y) = f_s((-x)+x+y) = f_s(-x+(x+y)) \subseteq f_s(-x) \cup f_s(x+y) = f_s(x) \cup f_s(x+y) = f_s(x+y)$$

Since by equation (1), $f_s(x) \subseteq f_s(y)$ for all $y \in S$ and $x, y \in S$, implies that $x+y \in S$. Thus, it follows that $f_s(x) \subseteq f_s(x+y)$. So $f_s(x+y) = f_s(y)$ for all $y \in S$.

Now, let $x \in S$. Then, for all $x, y \in S$

$$f_s(y+x) = f_s(y+x+(y-y)) = f_s(y+(x+y)-y) \subseteq f_s(y) \cup f_s(x+y) \cup f_s(-y) = f_s(y) \cup f_s(x+y) = f_s(y)$$

Since $f_s(x+y) = f_s(y)$. Furthermore, for all $y \in S$

$$f_s(y) = f_s(y+(x-x)) = f_s((y+x)-x) \subseteq f_s(y+x) \cup f_s(-x) = f_s(y+x) \cup f_s(x) = f_s(y+x) \text{ by equation (1).}$$

It follows that $f_s(y+x) = f_s(y)$ and so $f_s(x+y) = f_s(y+x) = f_s(y)$, for all $y \in S$, which completes the proof.

3.4 Theorem:

Let S be a near-field and f_s be a fuzzy soft set over U. If $f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(1) = f_s(x)$ for all $0 \neq x \in S$, then it is fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U.

Proof:

Suppose that $f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(1) = f_s(x)$ for all $0 \neq x \in S$.

In order to prove that it is fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U, it is enough to prove that $f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y)$ and $f_s(nx) \subseteq f_s(x)$.

Let $x, y \in S$. Then we have the following cases:

Case-1: Suppose that $x \neq 0$ and $y=0$ or $x=0$ and $y \neq 0$. Since S is a near-field, so it follows that $nx=0$ and $f_s(nx) = f_s(0)$. since $f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(x)$, for all $x \in S$, so $f_s(nx) = f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(x)$, and $f_s(nx) = f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(y)$. This imply $f_s(nx) \subseteq f_s(x)$.

Case-2: Suppose that $x \neq 0$ and $y \neq 0$. It follows that $nx \neq 0$. Then, $f_s(nx) = f_s(1) = f_s(x)$ and $f_s(nx) = f_s(1) = f_s(y)$, which implies that $f_s(nx) \subseteq f_s(x)$.

Case-3: suppose that $x=0$ and $y=0$, then clearly $f_s(nx) \subseteq f_s(x)$. Hence $f_s(nx) \subseteq f_s(x)$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Now, let $x, y \in S$. Then $x-y=0$ or $x-y \neq 0$. If $x-y=0$, then either $x=y=0$ or $x \neq 0, y \neq 0$ and $x=y$.

But, since $f_s(x-y) = f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(x)$, for all $x \in N$, it follows that $f_s(x-y) = f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y)$.

If $x-y \neq 0$, then either $x \neq 0, y \neq 0$ and $x \neq y$ or $x \neq 0$ and $y=0$ or $x=0$ and $y \neq 0$.

Assume that $x \neq 0, y \neq 0$ and $x \neq y$. This follows that

$$f_s(x-y) = f_s(1) = f_s(x) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y).$$

Now, let $x \neq 0$ and $y=0$. Then $f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y)$. Finally, let $x=0$ and $y \neq 0$.

Then, $f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y)$. Hence $f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y)$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Thus, f_s is fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U.

3.5 Theorem:

Let f_s and f_T be two fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U. Then $f_s \wedge f_T$ is fuzzy soft SU-action on N-module over U.

Proof: let $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2) \in S \times T$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} f_{S \wedge T}((x_1, y_1) - (x_2, y_2)) &= f_{S \wedge T}(x_1 - x_2, y_1 - y_2) \\ &= f_s(x_1 - x_2) \cap f_T(y_1 - y_2) \\ &\subseteq (f_s(x_1) \cup f_s(x_2)) \cap (f_T(y_1) \cup f_T(y_2)) \\ &= (f_s(x_1) \cup f_T(y_1)) \cap (f_s(x_2) \cup f_T(y_2)) \\ &= f_{S \wedge T}(x_1, y_1) \cap f_{S \wedge T}(x_2, y_2) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} f_{S \wedge T}((n_1, n_2), (x_2, y_2)) &= f_{S \wedge T}(n_1 x_2, n_2 y_2) \\ &= f_s(n_1 x_2) \cap f_T(n_2 y_2) \\ &\subseteq f_s(x_2) \cap f_T(y_2) \\ &= f_{S \wedge T}(x_2, y_2) \end{aligned}$$

Thus $f_s \wedge f_T$ is fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U.

Note that $f_s \vee f_T$ is not fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U.

3.2 Example:

Assume $U = p_3$ is the universal set. Let $S = Z_3$ and $H = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} a & a \\ b & b \end{bmatrix} / a, b \in Z_3 \right\}$ 2×2 matrices with Z_3 terms, be set of parameters. We define fuzzy SU-action on N-module f_S over $U = p_3$ by

$$\begin{aligned} f_S(0) &= p_3 \\ f_S(1) &= \{(1), (1\ 2), (1\ 3\ 2)\} \\ f_S(2) &= \{(1), (1\ 2), (1\ 2\ 3), (1\ 3\ 2)\} \end{aligned}$$

We define fuzzy SU-action on N-module f_H over $U = p_3$ by

$$\begin{aligned} f_H \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} &= p_3 \\ f_H \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \right\} &= \{(1), (1\ 2), (1\ 3\ 2)\} \end{aligned}$$

Then $f_s \vee f_T$ is not fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U..

3.2 Definition:

Let f_s, g_T be fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U. Then product of fuzzy SU-action on N-module f_s and g_T is defined as $f_s \times g_T = h_{S \times T}$, where $h_{S \times T}(x, y) = f_s(x) \times g_T(y)$ for all $(x, y) \in S \times T$.

3.6 Theorem:

If f_s and g_T are fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U. Then so is $f_s \times g_T$ over $U \times U$.

Proof:

By definition-3.2, let $f_S \times g_T = h_{S \times T}$, where $h_{S \times T}(x, y) = f_S(x) \times g_T(y)$ for all $(x, y) \in S \times T$. Then for all $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2) \in S \times T$ and $(n_1, n_2) \in N \times N$.

$$\begin{aligned} h_{S \times T}((x_1, y_1) - (x_2, y_2)) &= h_{S \times T}(x_1 - x_2, y_1 - y_2) \\ &= f_S(x_1 - x_2) \times g_T(y_1 - y_2) \\ &\subseteq (f_S(x_1) \cup f_S(x_2)) \times (g_T(y_1) \cup g_T(y_2)) \\ &= (f_S(x_1) \times g_T(y_1)) \cup (f_S(x_2) \times g_T(y_2)) \\ &= h_{S \times T}(x_1, y_1) \cup h_{S \times T}(x_2, y_2) \\ h_{S \times T}((n_1, n_2)(x_2, y_2)) &= h_{S \times T}(n_1 x_2, n_2 y_2) \\ &= f_S(n_1 x_2) \times g_T(n_2 y_2) \\ &\subseteq f_S(x_2) \times g_T(y_2) \\ &= h_{S \times T}(x_2, y_2) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f_S \times g_T = h_{S \times T}$ is fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U.

3.7 Theorem:

If f_S and h_S are fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U, then so is $f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S$ over U.

Proof:

Let $x, y \in S$ and $n \in N$ then

$$\begin{aligned} (f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S)(x-y) &= f_S(x-y) \cap h_S(x-y) \\ &\subseteq (f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)) \cap (h_S(x) \cup h_S(y)) \\ &= (f_S(x) \cap h_S(x)) \cup (f_S(y) \cap h_S(y)) \\ &= (f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S)(x) \cup (f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S)(y) \\ (f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S)(nx) &= f_S(nx) \cap h_S(nx) \\ &\subseteq f_S(x) \cap h_S(x) \\ &= (f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S)(x) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $(f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S)$ is fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U.

4. SU-Action on N-Ideal Structures:

4.1 Definition:

Let S be an N-module and f_S be a fuzzy soft set over U. Then f_S is called fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of S over U if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (i) $f_S(x + y) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)$
- (ii) $f_S(-x) = f_S(x)$
- (iii) $f_S(x + y - x) \subseteq f_S(y)$
- (iv) $f_S(n(x + y) - nx) \subseteq f_S(y)$ for all $x, y \in S$ and $n \in N$.

Here, note that $f_S(x + y) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)$ and $f_S(-x) = f_S(x)$ imply $f_S(x - y) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)$

4.1 Example:

Consider the near -ring $N = \{0, x, y, z\}$ with the following tables

+	0	x	y	z
0	0	x	y	z
x	x	0	z	y
y	y	z	0	x
z	z	y	x	0

.	0	x	y	z
0	0	0	0	0
x	0	0	0	x
y	0	x	y	y
z	0	x	y	z

Let $S=N$ be the parameters and $U= D_2$, dihedral group, be the universal set. We define a fuzzy soft set f_S over U by $f_S(0) = D_2$, $f_S(x) = \{e, b, ba\}$, $f_S(y) = \{a, b\}$, $f_S(z) = \{b\}$.

Then, one can show that f_S is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of S over U.

4.2 Example:

Consider the near -ring $N = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ with the following tables

+	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	2	3	0
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	0	1	2

.	0	x	y	z
0	0	0	0	0
x	0	1	0	1
y	0	3	0	3
z	0	2	0	2

Let $S=N$ be the set of parameters and $U= Z^+$ be the universal set. We define a fuzzy soft set f_S over U by

$$\begin{aligned} f_S(0) &= \{1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 17\} \\ f_S(1) &= f_S(3) = \{1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11\} \\ f_S(2) &= \{1, 5, 7, 9, 11\} \end{aligned}$$

Since $f_s(2.(3 + 1) - 2.3) = f_s(2.1 - 2.3) = f_s(3 - 3) = f_s(0) \not\subseteq f_s(1)$

Therefore, f_s is not fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal over U. It is known that if N is a zero- symmetric near-ring, then every N-ideal of S is also N-module of S. Here, we have an analog for this case.

4.1 Theorem:

Let N be a zero- symmetric near-ring. Then, every fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal is fuzzy SU-action on N-module over U.

Proof:

Let f_s be an fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal on S over U. Since $f_s(n(x+y)-nx) \subseteq f_s(y)$, for all $x,y \in S$, and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, in particular for $x=0$, it follows that $f_s(n(0+y)-n.0) = f_s(ny-0) = f_s(y) \subseteq f_s(y)$.

Since the other condition is satisfied by definition-4.1, f_s is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideals of S over U.

4.2 Theorem:

Let f_s be fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of S and f_T be fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of T over U. Then $f_s \wedge f_T$ is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of $S \times T$ over U.

4.3 Theorem:

If f_s is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of S and f_T be fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of T over U, then $f_s \times f_T$ is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal over $U \times U$.

4.4 Theorem:

If f_s and h_s are two fuzzy SU-action on N-modules of S over U, then $f_s \tilde{\cap} h_s$ is Fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal over U.

5. Application of Fuzzy SU-Action on N-Module:

In this section, we give the applications of fuzzy soft image, soft pre-image, lower α -inclusion of fuzzy soft sets and N-module homomorphism with respect to fuzzy SU-action on N-modules and N-ideals.

5.1 Theorem:

If f_s is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of S over U, then $S^f = \{x \in S / f_s(x) = f_s(0)\}$ is a N-ideal of S.

Proof:

It is obvious that $0 \in S^f$ we need to show that (i) $x-y \in S^f$, (ii) $s+x-s \in S^f$ and (iii) $n(s+x)-ns \in S^f$ for all $x,y \in S^f$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s \in S$.

If $x,y \in S^f$, then $f_s(x) = f_s(y) = f_s(0)$. By proposition-3.1,

$f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(x-y)$, $f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(s+x-s)$, and $f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(n(s+x)-ns)$ for all $x,y \in S^f$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s \in S$.

Since f_s is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of S over U, then for all $x,y \in S^f$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s \in S$.

$$(i) f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y) = f_s(0).$$

$$(ii) f_s(s+x-s) \subseteq f_s(x) = f_s(0).$$

$$(iii) f_s(n(s+x)-ns) \subseteq f_s(x) = f_s(0).$$

Hence $f_s(x-y) = f_s(0)$, $f_s(s+x-s) = f_s(0)$ and $f_s(n(s+x)-ns) = f_s(0)$, for all $x,y \in S^f$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s \in S$.

Therefore S^f is N-ideal of S.

5.2 Theorem:

Let f_s be fuzzy soft set over U and α be a subset of U such that $\emptyset \supseteq \alpha \supseteq f_s(0)$. If f_s is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal over U, then $f_s^{\subseteq \alpha}$ is an N-ideal of S.

Proof:

Since $f_s(0) \subseteq \alpha$, then $0 \in f_s^{\subseteq \alpha}$ and $\emptyset \neq f_s^{\subseteq \alpha} \supseteq S$. Let $x,y \in f_s^{\subseteq \alpha}$, then $f_s(x) \subseteq \alpha$ and $f_s(y) \subseteq \alpha$. We need to show that

$$(i) x-y \in f_s^{\subseteq \alpha}$$

$$(ii) s+x-s \in f_s^{\subseteq \alpha}$$

$$(iii) n(s+x)-ns \in f_s^{\subseteq \alpha} \text{ for all } x,y \in f_s^{\subseteq \alpha} \text{ and } n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ and } s \in S.$$

Since f_s is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal over U, it follows that

$$(i) f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y) \subseteq \alpha \cup \alpha = \alpha,$$

$$(ii) f_s(s+x-s) \subseteq f_s(x) \subseteq \alpha \text{ and}$$

$$(iii) f_s(n(s+x)-ns) \subseteq f_s(x) \subseteq \alpha. \text{ Thus, the proof is completed.}$$

5.3 Theorem:

Let f_s and f_T be fuzzy soft sets over U and χ be an N-isomorphism from S to T. If f_s is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of S over U, then $\chi(f_s)$ is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of T over U.

Proof:

Let δ_1, δ_2 and $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Since χ is surjective, there exists $s_1, s_2 \in S$ such that $\chi(s_1) = \delta_1$ and $\chi(s_2) = \delta_2$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\chi f_s)(\delta_1 - \delta_2) &= \cup \{ f_s(s) / s \in S, \chi(s) = \delta_1 - \delta_2 \} \\ &= \cup \{ f_s(s) / s \in S, s = \chi^{-1}(\delta_1 - \delta_2) \} \\ &= \cup \{ f_s(s) / s \in S, s = \chi^{-1}(\chi(s_1 - s_2)) = s_1 - s_2 \} \\ &= \cup \{ f_s(s_1 - s_2) / s_i \in S, \chi(s_i) = \delta_i, i = 1, 2, \dots \} \\ &\subseteq \cup \{ f_s(s_1) \cup f_s(s_2) / s_i \in S, \chi(s_i) = \delta_i, i = 1, 2, \dots \} \end{aligned}$$

$$= (\{\cup \{f_s(s_1)/s_1 \in S, \chi(s_1) = \delta_1\}\} \cup \{\cup \{f_s(s_2)/s_2 \in S, \chi(s_2) = \delta_2\}\}) \\ = (\chi(f_s))(\delta_1) \cup (\chi(f_s))(\delta_2)$$

$$\text{Also } (\chi(f_s))(\delta_1 + \delta_2 - \delta_1) = \cup \{f_s(s) / s \in S, \chi(s) = \delta_1 + \delta_2 - \delta_1\} \\ = \cup \{f_s(s) / s \in S, s = \chi^{-1}(\delta_1 + \delta_2 - \delta_1)\} \\ = \cup \{f_s(s) / s \in S, s = \chi^{-1}(\chi(s_1 + s_2 - s_1)) = s_1 + s_2 - s_1\} \\ = \cup \{f_s(s_1 + s_2 - s_1) / s_i \in S, \chi(s_i) = \delta_i, i = 1, 2, \dots\} \\ \subseteq \cup \{f_s(s_2) / s_2 \in S, \chi(s_2) = \delta_2\} \\ = (\chi(f_s))(\delta_2)$$

$$\text{Furthermore, } (\chi(f_s))(n(\delta_1 + \delta_2) - n\delta_1) = \cup \{f_s(s) / s \in S, \chi(s) = n(\delta_1 + \delta_2) - n\delta_1\} \\ = \cup \{f_s(s) / s \in S, s = \chi^{-1}(n(\delta_1 + \delta_2) - n\delta_1)\} \\ = \cup \{f_s(s) / s \in S, s = n(s_1 + s_2) - ns_1\} \\ = \cup \{f_s(n(s_1 + s_2) - ns_1) / s_i \in S, \chi(s_i) = \delta_i, i = 1, 2, \dots\} \\ \subseteq \cup \{f_s(s_2) / s_2 \in S, \chi(s_2) = \delta_2\} \\ = (\chi(f_s))(\delta_2).$$

Hence $\chi(f_s)$ is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of T over U.

5.4 Theorem:

Let f_s and f_T be fuzzy soft sets over U and χ be an N-isomorphism from S to T. If f_T is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of T over U, then $\chi^{-1}(f_T)$ is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of S over U.

Proof:

$$\text{Let } s_1, s_2 \in S \text{ and } n \in \mathbb{N}. \text{ Then} \\ (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(s_1 - s_2) = f_T(\chi(s_1 - s_2)) \\ = f_T(\chi(s_1) - \chi(s_2)) \\ \subseteq f_T(\chi(s_1)) \cup f_T(\chi(s_2)) \\ = (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(s_1) \cup (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(s_2).$$

$$\text{Also } (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(s_1 + s_2 - s_1) = f_T(\chi(s_1 + s_2 - s_1)) \\ = f_T(\chi(s_1) + \chi(s_2) - \chi(s_1)) \\ \subseteq f_T(\chi(s_2)) = (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(s_2)$$

$$\text{Furthermore, } (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(n(s_1 + s_2) - ns_1) = f_T(\chi(n(s_1 + s_2) - ns_1)) \\ = f_T(n(\chi(s_1) + \chi(s_2)) - n\chi(s_1)) \\ \subseteq f_T(\chi(s_2)) = (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(s_2)$$

Hence, $(\chi^{-1}(f_T))$ is fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal of S over U.

Conclusion:

In this paper, we have defined a new type of N-module action on a fuzzy soft set, called fuzzy SU-action on N-module by using the soft sets. This new concept picks up the soft set theory, fuzzy theory and N-module theory together and therefore, it is very functional for obtaining results in the mean of N-module structure. Based on this definition, we have introduced the concept of fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal. We have investigated these notions with respect to soft image, soft pre-image and lower α -inclusion of soft sets. Finally, we give some application of fuzzy SU-action on N-ideal to N-module theory. To extend this study, one can further study the other algebraic structures such as different algebra in view of their SU-actions.

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